

README – Dataset Description

Title:

Valorization of Bio-waste Wild Olive Leaves with Blue Pea Flower and Sea Buckthorn Berries: Optimization and Characterization of a Functional Instant Tea Tablet

Description:

This dataset supports the above-mentioned manuscript and includes experimental data generated during the study. The dataset contains physicochemical properties, antioxidant activities, bioactive compounds, enzymatic inhibition data, mineral composition, and sensory evaluation results.

Contents:

- Instant_Tea_Tablet_Data.xlsx: Contains physicochemical, antioxidant, bioactive, enzymatic, and mineral data.
- Sensory_Data_Exact_Mean_SD_Final.xlsx: Contains sensory evaluation data (n = 90 panelists), structured to reflect reported mean and standard deviation values.

Notes:

- All data are provided in processed form to support reproducibility of results.
- No personal or sensitive participant information is included.
- The dataset is publicly shared to comply with journal data-sharing policies.

Contact:

Corresponding Author: Syed Arsalan Ali